

TURNkey - Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

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Towards more Earthquake-resilient Urban Societies through a Multi-sensor-based Information System enabling Earthquake Forecasting, Early Warning and Rapid Response actions

TURNkey

Deliverable D3.11

Demonstrator for the estimation of seismic magnitude using citizen information from smartphone apps (EEW) – (Joint Deliverable with RISE project)

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LIST OF PARTNERS

Participant	Name	Country
NOR	Stiftelsen NORSAR	Norway
DEL	Stichting Deltares	Netherlands
KNMI	Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut	Netherlands
BRGM	Bureau de Recherches Géologiques et Minières	France
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
UIce	Haskoli Islands (University of Iceland)	Iceland
EUC	Fondazione Eucentre	Italy
UStr	University of Strathclyde	UK
BUW	Bauhaus-Universität Weimar	Germany
UA	Universidad de Alicante	Spain
ARU	Anglia Ruskin University Higher Education Corporation	UK
UNIBG	Università degli Studi di Bergamo	Italy
UCL	University College London	UK
INFP	Institutul National de Cercetare si Dezvoltare pentru Fizica Pamantului	Romania
YET	YetItMoves S.r.l.	Italy
GMP	Gempa GmbH	Germany
NOA	National Observatory of Athens	Greece
NTC	Nutcracker Research Ltd.	UK
B80	Beta 80 SpA	Italy
Sim	Siminn hf.	Iceland
UPat	Panepistimio Patron (University of Patras)	Greece

GLOSSARY

Acronym	Description
EMSC	Euro-Mediterranean Seismology Centre
FAME	Felt Area for Magnitude Estimate

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INTRODUCTION

The objective of the proposed method is to offer a qualitative estimate of the magnitude of felt earthquakes (occurring globally) for which location and magnitude are not rapidly available. This estimate is based on the size of the felt area and is derived from LastQuake app-launch data. This method answers a specific need of the EMSC's rapid public information system. Indeed, with an ever-growing number of LastQuake app users, EMSC detects, through surges in app launches, small magnitude earthquakes (down to $M \sim 1$ in certain regions) for which earthquake parameters (location and magnitude) may not be available for many hours to even days. We, therefore, aim at providing to our users qualitative information on the earthquake magnitude (small or not small) from the fastest data obtained: the location and time of LastQuake app launches.

It is not possible to make an accurate estimate of the magnitude from our dataset and thus, our goal is somewhat more pragmatic: we aim at rapidly informing our users whether they have just felt a small-magnitude local earthquake or a more significant event. Once fully validated, we plan to publish the results of this approach, named FAME (Felt Area for Magnitude Estimate), through our LastQuake system comprising a Twitter quakebot, a website for mobile devices and an app.

This development complements a study performed in the framework of the RISE project by Gianfranco Vanucci and Paolo Gasperini by exploiting their method named BOXER to derive both magnitude and epicentral location from felt reports (Gasperini, et al., 1999; Gasperini, et al., 2010), the potential advantage of FAME being, at least theoretically, faster.

DATA AND METHOD

The data exploited are LastQuake app launches, i.e., the time and location when a user opened the LastQuake app. A surge in app launches allows the rapid detection of felt earthquakes regardless of seismic data, as well as the mapping of the felt area (Bossu, et al., 2019). App launches reflect information-seeking behaviour and are triggered by eyewitnesses feeling a tremor, turning the eyewitnesses into near-real-time sensors (Bossu, et al., 2019).

The app launches will be exploited in a time window ranging from 30 s before the trigger (before which an increase in app launches is non-existent or very weak) and up to 150 s after the trigger. App launches after the notification are disregarded as notifications themselves generate their own launches beyond the felt area. If a notification is published before the end of the estimation process, the process is stopped and no estimation is published. Because there may be app launches not linked to any tremor, especially in regions with a high density of LastQuake app users, geometric characteristics of the felt area will be evaluated using both app launches and the local number of app users to limit the impact of outliers.

A multi-layer perceptron classifier is used to estimate if an earthquake is small or not in near real-time. A curve of prediction is then drawn as a function of the monitoring delay and scored in order to determine whether the estimate is reliable.

More details on the method can be found in the technical deliverable (D3.10.)

DEVELOPMENT AND DEPLOYMENT

The service is built for Python 3.6-3.8 with direct access to the EMSC databases. An estimate is performed every time an app-trigger is sent through the messenger RabbitMQ. The whole process was built by trial-and-error. Hence, the performance during this test phase left room for improvement. The test phase is hopefully now at its end (end of Aug. 2021).

The screenshot shows a web browser displaying the 'Felt Area for Magnitude Estimates (FAME)' page. The page title is 'Felt Area for Magnitude Estimates (FAME)'. Below the title is a 'Table of contents' with three links: '1. FAME for users', '2. FAME for scientists', and '3. FAME for maintainers'. The main content area starts with the text: 'An earthquake is considered as small if its magnitude is smaller than or equal to 4. The figures and tables of this page are updated once per hour.' This is followed by a section header '1. FAME for users' and a sub-section '0.1. Last prediction'. The prediction details are as follows:

- Last prediction FzinN6
- Sun, 05 Sep 2021 @ 11:15:05 UTC
- Estimated to be a small earthquake
- probability: 99.1%
- confidence: 97.9%
- Monitoring delay: 20 s
- Prediction delay: 30 s 19 hours and 45 minutes ago
- Associated to evid 1 032 027
- magnitude: 3.6
- region: Near The Coast Of Western Turkey
- Correct estimate

At the bottom of the screenshot, there is a caption: 'FIG. 1 - PREDICTION ASSOCIATED TO THE LAST APP-TRIGGER. NOT ASSOCIATED MEANS THAT THE TRIGGER IS NOT YET ASSOCIATED TO AN EARTHQUAKE AND MIGHT NEVER BE.'

Figure 0.1 Screenshot of the top of the performance web-page (<https://www.emsc-csem.org/Earthquake/FAME/readme.html>)

The increase of the accuracy of our classifier is encouraging. However, the increase and stability of the success rate must be confirmed for a longer period in order to process a variety of cases. Indeed, we have observed errors of predictions during large earthquakes, which hopefully will no longer occur in the future due to a recent upgrade of the code. The new service will be provided to our users, once the success rate of the estimates is sufficiently satisfying over a certain time period (~ 1 month).

Due to the small quantity of data and app-triggers, it may take a while before reaching success rates that allow publishing the estimates. Another point to consider is how the estimates may be published based on the accuracy of our model as misinterpretations may occur. Especially around the chosen magnitude threshold, uncertainties of the estimate will be more important and this fact will have to be communicated during the publication of the estimates.

There is currently no demonstrator available for the FAME project. However, the background processes are operational and ready to be deployed on a dedicated machine. The performances of the development phase are available online with a series of figures that seek to show the evolution of the performance, but also highlight in which cases the classifier did not succeed (Figure 0.1, <https://www.emsc-csem.org/Earthquake/FAME/readme.html>). The list of the predictions is also available online (Figure 0.2, https://www.emsc-csem.org/Earthquake/FAME/list_of_predictions.php).

Date & Time [UTC]	Region	Trigger ID	Earthquake ID	Magnitude		Estimated to be	Probability of being small	Confidence	Monitoring delay [s]	Classifier ID	Estimate accuracy	Comments
				First	Final							
2021-09-06 00:53:15	Croatia	VD0SL8	1032165	1.7	2.6							fast association
2021-09-05 11:15:05	New The Coast Of Western Turkey	FziaN6	1032027	3.6	3.6	SMALL	99.1%	97.9%	20	20210901100646	CORRECT	
2021-09-03 05:17:00	Greece	e6ATQz	1031329	3.4	3.4	NOT SMALL	2.7%	80.6%	100	20210901100646	INCORRECT	
2021-09-02 18:37:45	Greece	thkB-0	1031148	3.4	3.2	SMALL	98.0%	81.5%	20	20210901100646	CORRECT	
2021-09-02 14:47:50	Greece	2B-pIA	1031106	3.7	3.4	SMALL	99.5%	99.3%	20	20210901100646	CORRECT	
2021-09-02 05:49:40	Greece	iaED5j	1030971	4.1	4.1	SMALL	99.8%	99.5%	20	20210901100646	INCORRECT	
2021-09-01 12:53:35	Strait Of Gibraltar	LzroIr	1030732	4.1	3.6	NOT SMALL	0.0%	97.4%	40	20210901100646	Incorrect???	
2021-09-01 10:35:05	Romania	UxLFud	1030692	4.5	4.4	NOT SMALL	0.0%	99.6%	90	20210901000831	CORRECT	
2021-09-01 07:13:44	Croatia	lej_2H	1030653	2.9	3.2							fast association
2021-09-01 05:05:53	Croatia	5pTxNz	1030626	1.5	1.5							fast association
2021-08-31 20:40:50	Crete, Greece	_ZwNu7	1030523	3.2	3.2	SMALL	100.0%	100.0%	20	20210825100333	CORRECT	
2021-08-31 11:37:05	Croatia	LMfDeV	1030283	1.7	1.8	SMALL	99.8%	93.5%	20	20210825100333	CORRECT	
2021-08-31 11:06:30	Western Turkey	4994FL	1030269	5.0	5.1	NOT SMALL	0.0%	99.9%	40	20210825100333	CORRECT	
2021-08-30 23:13:50	Baja California, Mexico	zMKGwX	1030022	2.7	3.0	SMALL	92.6%	92.4%	20	20210825100333	CORRECT	
2021-08-29 21:07:05	Southern Greece	YFa-lp	1029988	4.1	4.1							fast association
2021-08-29 18:16:30	Greece	pg67Te	1029628	3.6	3.2	SMALL	99.8%	99.8%	20	20210825100333	CORRECT	
2021-08-29 14:12:55	Crete, Greece	L1Tbh9	1029583	3.2	3.2	SMALL	95.5%	95.4%	20	20210825100333	CORRECT	
2021-08-29 06:42:45		yho019				SMALL	100.0%	98.9%	20	20210825100333		Not associated
2021-08-28 21:20:25	Croatia	aTwshA	1029307	1.6	1.6	SMALL	100.0%	95.7%	20	20210825100333	CORRECT	
2021-08-28 19:23:10	Crete, Greece	UzbodM	1029278	3.2	3.2	SMALL	97.9%	97.7%	20	20210825100333	CORRECT	
2021-08-28 11:23:15	Strait Of Gibraltar	HbNGWP	1029108	4.5	5.1	NOT SMALL	1.2%	90.4%	80	20210825100333	CORRECT	
2021-08-27 12:36:15	Central California	G-yXhi	1028822	3.9	3.9	SMALL	100.0%	100.0%	20	20210825100333	CORRECT	
2021-08-27 10:25:15	Mindanao, Philippines	C8jzcK	1028771	5.9	5.6	SMALL	100.0%	100.0%	20	20210825100333	INCORRECT	

Figure 0.2 Web-page showing the list of predictions (https://www.emsc-csem.org/Earthquake/FAME/list_of_predictions.php).

CONCLUSIONS

The FAME project aims at telling the EMSC users if an earthquake is probably small or not thanks to their active participation on the LastQuake app. The method is now well established and the first applications of the method were very promising. However, the estimates are not yet ready to be published as part of the services offered by the EMSC. Indeed, the service needs more time to improve and deliver reliable results.

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